

Vegan Animal Mortality Assessment Report (VAMAR):

An evaluation of the animal mortality of fully plant-based diets.

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Abstract:

A debate regarding ethical consequences of diets has often seen an assumption that vegan diets are the most effective in reducing animal deaths. Conversely, recent analysis suggests that plant-based agricultural systems directly and indirectly cause a higher number of animal deaths due to habitat loss and planting-related mortality.

This paper (VAMAR) compares an estimation of animal deaths with 100% vegan diets vs diets that include animal products, with the main differences appearing between crop yields, livestock conversion ratios, plant biomass waste (non-human-edible), crop protection industry direct harm (shootings), and how it all relates to mortality in terms of calories and nutrients.

The goal of our paper is to answer the question:

With focus on the United States, Canada and Europe, what food choice can the average consumer make, that would cause the least animal death?

Results indicate that, under the current system, 100% plant-based diets would contribute to a larger number of deaths of animals than a diet that includes meat (mainly ruminants) in its cycle. This advantage of including animals comes from two main areas:

1. The grass-fed, pasture-raised cattle being raised with minimal input of pesticides;
2. From animal agriculture ability to upcycle non-human-edible plant biomass into usable and useful nutrients for humans.

These findings highlight the complexity of ethical dietary choices and suggest that, in order to minimise harm, one has to consider the direct and indirect forms of mortality in food production systems.

Introduction

The ethical evaluation of human diets has increasingly turned to the question of animal mortality. Advocates of veganism often argue that avoiding animal products minimises harm by eliminating the need for slaughter. This claim has intuitive appeal: livestock are directly killed for meat, milk, and eggs, whereas plant-based foods appear to involve no deliberate killing of sentient beings.

Popular summaries (e.g., Animal Visuals, 2009)¹ have amplified this claim, framing it in terms of “deaths per million kilocalories”. More recently, Fischer and Lamey (2018)² have noted that the empirical basis for these estimates is sparse, geographically limited, and prone to overgeneralisation. Nonetheless, the debate has entered both academic and public discourse; how are “least harm” arguments in food ethics assessed?

Pesticide use takes front stage in our investigation. Crop agriculture relies heavily on chemical inputs that directly kill vast numbers of invertebrates and indirectly affect birds, mammals, amphibians, and other fauna and flora. Meanwhile, the production of animal products also requires cropland, especially for feed, but ruminant systems can convert non-human-edible biomass into food.

This conversion, also known as “upcycling”, maybe sufficient to cover the animal cost, and is something that few papers have touched on. Whether vegan diets truly reduce or increase animal mortality depends on these complex factors (slaughter, field deaths, pesticide impact, upcycling and feed allocation).

Despite the intensity of the debate, the literature remains limited by methodological inconsistencies. Studies differ in their choice of metric (calories vs protein vs nutrient adequacy), the measuring direct vs indirect killing, and the allocation of feed-crop impacts.

This paper (VAMAR) will address the claims from both sides, starting with the summary from Animal Visuals. This summary is a popular tool used in ethical debates regarding veganism and, with this as a base, our study will address common misconceptions and raise the option of pasture-raise beef, the pesticide industry’s impact on animal death, and then move to a more global scale and the feasibility of replacing animal foods with plant-based foods in regard to macronutrients, micronutrients and calories.

The present study addresses these gaps by systematically comparing omnivorous and vegan diets across multiple direct and indirect mortality categories: slaughter, field kills and pesticide impacts.

The aim is not to settle the ethical debate but to clarify the empirical foundations of the claim that vegan diets minimise harm, focusing on a practical measure: the number of casualties (as opposed to value of insect’s vs mammals for example).

By making assumptions transparent and quantifying uncertainty, we provide a more rigorous basis for evaluating “least harm” arguments in diet ethics for the future.

Animal Visuals, a famous popular mistake:

The summary provided by Animal Visuals¹ [AV] is a commonly cited source in vegan circles when the topic of animal mortality emerges. These numbers, based on the reports of *Davis et al*³ and *Gaverick et al*⁴, were for many years the end-all be-all of the discussion, “proving” that a vegan diet would immensely reduce the number of deaths when measured in terms of calories provided per animals death.

The following graph provides an indication of the whole document:

Fig1- Number of deaths per million calories in 8 different food categories¹.

The AV summary’s first oversight is misreporting the amount of calories provided by the animals, but our study will mainly focus on beef production. The AV summary claims 1.7 deaths per 1 million calories (Mcal) at slaughter time.

The average cow in the United Kingdom (UK) at the time of slaughter is, on average, 630kg⁵. Let us consider the calories of the whole animal:

Component	Kcal Contribution
Meat	~550,000 kcal
Fat	~178,000 kcal
Organs	~18,000 kcal
Bone Marrow	~30,800 kcal
Blood	~20,550 kcal
Total	≈797,000 kcal

Using these numbers to reach 1Mcal we only need 1.255 animals to die. This is a 30% error margin of the original number of 1.7, and puts the animal death per Mcal at a lower number if we consider slaughter alone vs harvest in the original summary.

AV adds to the number of deaths in the animal section the “harvest” needed to feed the cow. The original author states that: “85% of beef is fed corn.” The author does not mention if these are corn kernels (human-edible) or stems, leaves, husks and cobs (non-human-edible).

This is the second oversight that often shows during these evaluations. The points presented by the author of AV would have some veracity if the animal in question, had been fed solely food that we could have used for humans. However, more often than not, the feed that goes to ruminants is composed of a majority, if not all (e.g. in grass-fed systems), of non-human-edible feed⁶.

To elaborate, for the purposes of this paper, by “non-human-edible”, we are referring to biomass that humans could consume, but it would not provide any benefit nutritionally and could potentially be detrimental to human health.

Since this non-human-edible biomass is an unavoidable result of the crop industry, beef production that feeds their animals these leftovers **would not be able to be held responsible for any deaths that were caused as a result.**

So, considering that crop production generates a large amount of non-human-edible biomass (40%-60% at best in the case of rice, and 85%-90% at worst in the case of corn), and we saw that, per Mcal, beef production causes fewer deaths than any other crop presented by the AV authors, a plausible inference is that, if the beef is fed non-human-edible crops, a mixture of crops and beef diets would be the diet that causes the least amount of animal deaths.

A common response to this counter-argument, is a study⁶ that shows that cows still need 2.8kg of human-edible food to produce 1 kg of meat. This study, however, focused entirely on muscle meat and discarded other factors such as organs or bone marrow.

But assuming that *Mottet et al.* were correct, there is still one more factor to consider: food waste.

In the “human-edible section”, it was assumed that all the food that was human-edible would be able to be fed to humans. But this is often not the case. Considering that some articles estimate unharvested produce at 33%⁷, while the WWF reported a 15% loss in crops even before it leaves the farm⁸, and that the total amount of farmed food waste before it even reaches the consumer could be as high as 44%⁹; it puts into perspective how much “human-edible food” that is going to animals actually is food that would be fed to humans or simply discarded without the presence of animal agriculture.

Furthermore, in 2022, according to journalistic reports¹⁰ and FAO¹¹, even when the food reaches the consumer, “2.1bn tonnes will either be lost or thrown away”. And according to this report¹² 70% of food waste comes from households. If both sources above are correct and we need 2.8 kg of human-edible feed to create 1 kg of meat⁶, then those 2.1 bn tonnes reported wasted would be enough to satisfy the world’s meat industry¹³.

All this food waste could be avoided if it was fed to animals, and in turn, these animals would create highly nutritious foods for humans.

Finally, the authors of the AV report fail to mention the nutritional value of beef vs. the crops fed to these animals. 100 g of corn would provide humans with 5 % of their daily nutritional needs. 100g of sirloin steak would provide 35% of the nutritional needs for a human. A 7x difference that would easily justify the growth of animals for food when compared to any of the previous papers cited so far¹⁴. If digestibility (DIAAS) would be taken into account, this difference would favour meat even more due to its high digestibility when compared to corn.

To sum up, the AV report is an improper representation of reality. When taking into account the full animal, the food waste, the non-edible biomass and finally the nutritional value, we can see that animal farming will actually reduce the number of animal deaths.

Veganism: How many actual deaths?

The AV author claims that the amount of animal deaths per 1Mcal from crops is between 1.65 and 2.55. Is this claim true?

We can see that the author used mice death before and after harvest to reach this number. There is a problem with this approach: Not only mice die in crop fields, and not only during the harvest. He conveniently left out the following animals:

Worms, Slugs, Snails, Ladybugs, Honeybees, Bumblebees, Butterflies, Lacewings, Voles, Shrews, Toads, Frogs, Snakes, Skylark, Hedgehog, Bats, Lizards, Red fox, Roe deer fawn, Badger, Mole, Cricket, Beetles, Spiders, Millipedes, Centipedes, Yellow jacket, Dragonfly, Moth, Ants, Weasels, Deer's, Hares, Rabbits, all birds and so many more animals.

Not to mention that the original author only measured combine harvest deaths and not ploughing, seeding, crop protection shootings, and, most importantly, pesticides.

When accounting for these factors, the number of deaths would be in the millions, if not billions, per 1Mcal¹⁵.

Fig2: Annual Animal Deaths¹¹

A clear example of this miscount is honeybees; it has been extensively documented the number of deaths caused by the direct use of honeybees in pollination of crops¹⁶ (caused by factors such as transportation), as well as the indirect killing of these animals through pesticide¹⁷ use.

Even without accounting for birds or vertebrates, the real number of deaths from pesticides alone (Fig2) far surpasses the one presented by the AV report.

This¹⁸ paper roughly calculates the animal death cost of crops being 7.3 billion per year in the US alone. The author states it may be a very conservative estimate

and, of course, not account for insects, amphibians and reptiles, as many species are not monitored. To put it into perspective, 7.3 billion crops deaths is 100x the number of all the cows and pigs consumed in the US combined¹⁹.

B. Ficher et al.'s paper mentions that if the lowball number of deaths is to be believed, then the number 7.3 billion deaths per year is exaggerated; Again, this number only accounts for a few mammals, fishes and birds. We are missing the numbers for small critters (frogs, spiders, worms, etc.) and for insects (bees, ants, etc.).

A Scenario Without Meat

A common counterargument to the points presented stems from the logic that feeding humans what animals eat would result in a smaller cropland necessity and therefore a reduction in pesticides and other crop-related deaths. This argument will appear gain in the section titled "Trophic Levels" but lets consider the land side of this argument.

By cropland this paper is referring to agricultural land that is suitable for growing human-edible crops. Not to be confused with farmland that includes pastures where animals are raised but no crops could sustainably grow (e.g., grasslands).

Because animals require a larger area than crops, this seems to be a reasonable argument. Further along, in this VAMAR paper, we will argue that farmland required for animals results in fewer animal deaths than cropland, even when comparing total farmland minus cropland vs. cropland.

This VAMAR paper has already shown the presence of animal's agriculture would reduce the total number of deaths in a best-case, ideal scenario. However, is this reduction in animal death present in the world as we live in today?

Without the presence of animal agriculture, would cropland decrease?*

In the short term YES, but it would have disastrous consequences for human food supply. Current agricultural methods are inefficient, and a lot of grain, corn and soy is grown for feed, which causes losses that are unnecessary in terms of both protein and calories.

However, we must acknowledge the points mentioned before. The biomass produced by plants that cannot be fed to humans, if fed to animals, would reduce cropland needs.

*The following section is based on US agriculture and data. It could be extrapolated to other developed countries with similar methods but not for undeveloped countries or locations.

Furthermore, pasture-raised animals would reduce the need for cropland. Whether pastureland or cropland will result in fewer animal deaths will be addressed in a later portion of this paper.

There is also the matter of waste products such as distiller grains, ethanol, oilseed meals and other byproducts of human use and how viable it is to convert such products to human consumption. Feeding these products to animals would again reduce the need for cropland.

Finally, humans cannot (and would not) eat raw feed grain mass exactly as animals do. Changing diets at scale requires food-processing capacity, changes in culinary patterns, and distribution adjustments. These factors affect actual usable protein and micronutrient availability (and possibly energy costs of processing). Supplementation would increase for B12 (non-existing in plants).

An extra point to consider is that an increase in cropland seems to result in a higher greenhouse gas (GHG) Emissions^{20 21 22}.

These last three paragraphs' calculations are beyond the scope of this paper. However, with the argument of reusing the inedible plant biomass as presented before, plus the argument that pastureland causes less animal death than cropland, we can see that a complete elimination of animal agriculture and consumption would result in a higher animal death rate.

The Pesticide Conundrum

What kills more animals? The animal industry or the pesticide industry? A simple way to answer this question is to look at the number of pesticides used by each and compare it to calories and nutrients produced.

a-c correspond to the consumption globally, in developed and economies in transition countries, and in developing countries, respectively.

Fig.3: Global Pesticide use and distribution²¹

In Fig.3, we see that the pesticide use is almost 5x higher for crops vs. for animal foods in developed worlds and almost 6x higher in developing Economies²¹. The same study mentions the inclusion on the "animal-based food section" the pesticides used in the production of crops that go to animals. As the author puts it:

"the pesticide footprints embedded in animal-based foods are stemmed from feed (e.g., grains, cereal residuals, oilcakes)"

This inclusion skews the result in favour of plant foods since we are including pesticide use for animal agriculture that may have not been directly grown for that purpose. However, this VAMAR paper will argue that even with such a handicap, the numbers still favour animal agriculture when it comes to pesticide use.

From this paper we extrapolate a pesticide use of cropland to animal pesticide use that is vastly different. It can go as low as 5-1 (when feeding animals crops and by-products) or as high, according to another source²³, as 30-1 (perhaps even higher when looking at crops such as potatoes when compared to grasslands).

Fig.4: Crop total Pesticide use²³

Due to the great difference between all these numbers, we will assume that a ratio of 5 to 1 is correct in order to give the best possible chance for vegan foods, which would translate to animal foods using one-fifth of the pesticides.

Do plant foods provide 5 times more calories and protein to justify a 5x use of pesticides?

No²⁴. According to the World in Data graphs, plant foods only provide about half the protein (58%) and 70% of total calories.

Daily protein supply from animal and plant-based foods, World, 2022

Daily per capita protein supply is measured in grams per person per day. Protein of animal origin includes protein from all meat commodities, eggs and dairy products, and fish & seafood.

Fig.5: Daily Protein supply⁽²⁴⁾

To break even, in the best-case scenario for vegan foods, these numbers should be 15% animal and 75% plant, and the numbers from OWD are far from it.

Does pasture-raised beef use even fewer pesticides? Research is lacking in a direct head-to-head comparison between pasture-raised and crop raised pesticide use.

Comparative analyses indicate that beef derived from pasture-raised (grass-fed) systems is associated with substantially lower upstream pesticide use per kilogram of product than feedlot (crop-fed) beef. Typical feed crops such as maize and soy receive approximately 3–6 kg of active pesticide ingredients per hectare annually, while permanent pastures or rangelands generally receive < 0.2 kg/ha/yr, often approaching zero in extensive grazing systems²⁵.

Land-use intensity for feedlot beef averages 10–15 m² per kg of beef, compared with 100–200 m² per kg for pasture-raised beef²⁶.

Combining these values yields an estimated pesticide input of roughly 3–9 g per kg beef for feedlot systems, versus 0–4 g per kg beef for pasture-based systems, corresponding to an approximate 50–99% reduction in pesticide use per kilogram of beef produced when animals are raised primarily on pasture rather than feed crops.

These results indicate that, with current farming methods, animal foods contribute to a significant reduction in pesticide use when fed crops and crop residues and an almost total elimination when fed in pastures.

A 100% pesticide elimination seems improbable since pasture-raised farmers must protect the animals against fleas, mosquitoes and other pests; However, it will have minimal effect on many other critters, birds and mammals, when compared to total field pesticide sprays seen in crop farming.

Trophic Levels

This seems counterintuitive, since we should be able to feed humans what animals eat and so reduce the amount of food produced according to the lesser energy waste caused by trophic levels' energy distribution.

"Feed the humans what we are feeding the animals" is inefficient, as this²⁷ article puts it:

"Cow-calf production consumes the least amount of Human-edible Protein (HeP) resulting in the greatest efficiency of HeP conversion and positively contributes to meeting human protein requirements. (...)When evaluated as a whole, the beef value chain is a net contributor to the HeP available for human consumption."

As mentioned before, the vast majority of harvested crops have a mostly non-human-edible component (anywhere from 40% to 90%); most of these foods are also very low in protein and nutrients accessible to humans (bioavailability).

Based on the data presented so far, the average crop uses more pesticides and, therefore, kills more animals than the average animal food **as long as crops are not grown solely for animal feed, and we don't feed solely the human-edible part to animals discarding to landfills the non-human-edible biomass.**

Some human-edible food does go directly from producer to animals but mostly after being rejected by human consumer re-sellers; if this was not fed to animals, it would be wasted. This death toll is accounted for in the previously mentioned source²¹ and still does not justify the statement that cows kill more animals than plant foods through their indirect use of pesticides.

The human food for feed:

Still, it was estimated that in some parts of the world, 2.8kg of human-edible feed is used for every 1kg of ruminants⁶ human-edible food.

Could we grow cows without that 2.8kg of food? Yes. Using a blend of pasture-raised and leftovers from human consumption, we could easily create a more sustainable and less deadly environment.

With all the facts presented, the claim that an increase in ruminant meat consumption would reduce the animal death seems plausible.

This would lead to the conclusion that if we wanted to reduce the animal's death toll, our first choice should be grass-fed and leftover-fed animal products, followed up by crops and lastly, crop-fed animals.

How can a regular person reduce their pesticide footprint and therefore their animal death toll? By choosing ruminants that are pasture raised and grass finished or by talking to the producers and visiting their farms.

Upcycling and Feed to Food Conversion

How are animals producing more food than what they consume?

To produce 1kg of meat, a cow would need around 35kg of pasture grass²⁸. However, grass is not human food; meat is. Bioavailability and digestibility must be considered. When fed grain, the estimates are around 8-1 (feed input to meat output).

As mentioned in the following publication²⁹, a study done in the UK shows that cows can output almost 3x the amount of protein that they ingest. This is mainly because of their ability to turn cellulose into amino acids.

"Given the perceived competition between animals and humans for feed and food, the most meaningful measure of feed efficiency in the future may be the ratio of human-edible protein input relative to the human-edible protein output. Wilkinson (2011) used this approach to compare different food production systems

in the United Kingdom. When expressed as the ratio of human-edible protein input per unit to edible animal protein output, milk was 0.71, various beef production systems were 0.92 to 3.00, pork was 2.6, poultry meat was 2.1, and eggs were 2.3.”

A more accurate statement would be that animals turn non-human-bioavailable protein into human-bioavailable protein. A process that we humans cannot replicate, to the same degree, in our bodies when consuming plants.

Since crops produce a large amount (40-90% of the total plant) of human non-edible biomass (grass, stalks, hulls, husks, etc) as well as products with lower bioavailability, and animals can convert these materials to extra protein and nutrients (B12 being the most prevalent in vegan discussion circles), the probability for veganism reducing the number of deaths is unlikely at this point in time.

How many Animals are killed in crop production?

Insects: 4.000.000.000.000.000+ due to insecticides³⁰

Birds: 670.000.000 (67million estimate in US * world area cropland)³¹

Fish: 100.000.000 (6m-14m in US alone)³²

Amphibians: Unknown (not measured)

Mammals: Unknown (not measured)

Would a higher demand for plant foods (vegan scenario) cause a higher animal death toll? Yes³³

This source on the biodiversity impact states that it is crops, not pastures, impacting biodiversity loss.

Fig. 2: Cumulated biodiversity impacts of land-use change in PSL_{glo} from 1995 to 2022 and the drivers in the global supply chain shown from different perspectives.

From: [Biodiversity impacts of recent land-use change driven by increases in agri-food imports](#)

Fig. 8: Impacts of Land Use³³

This is apparent in graph E of the study, where beef, dairy and eggs have a marginal impact when compared to vegan foods. Vegetables, fruit and nuts alone had a greater impact than all animal foods combined (which does not include rice and other vegan foods such as legumes). The authors account for the feed to animals in the impact caused by animal foods (again skewing the results against animal agriculture).

"If crops are used to feed animals, produce textiles (for example, cotton) or biochemicals (for example, bioplastics), the land-use change impacts of these crops are allocated to the produced commodities".

We could reduce the amount of human-edible food we give to animals and give it to people instead.

This shift would easily be done by switching our diet from monogastric animals to ruminants (cows). They can eat what humans can't and transform it into human-edible food at a lower life cost.

Eliminating cows and animals completely would cause the inedible biomass to go to "waste", and even if converted to more crops, this would cause a higher number of deaths per year due to pesticides. This is clear from the increased land use, biodiversity loss and pesticide use as the demand for vegan foods grows.

FEED or FOOD, which occupies more land?

According to *Ray et al. 2022*³⁴ The green area for food is many times larger than the blue area for feed.

Fig 9: Feed vs Food land use³⁴

The paper shows that in the 2010s **direct-food crops occupied substantially more harvested land than feed crops** (37% vs 18% of harvested hectares).

So, not only animals use less pesticides than crops, they also, currently, occupy less farmland.

Even if the crop-animal pesticide footprint per calorie/protein was equal, the difference in occupied land alone would show that Vegan foods kill more animals than animal agriculture due to the use of pesticides.

The FAT of the Matter

We have looked into calories, protein and, in a minor way nutrients. But fat consumption is also an essential part of the human diet^{35,36}.

Humans consume about 30-40 million tonnes of fat from animals (butter, tallow, lard etc).

Without animal agriculture, we would need to match the fat needs of humans with soybean oil (since it is the most cost-effective crop in terms of protein, nutrients and fat). Since most of the soy fed to animals is in the form of cake, with the fat/oil removed for use in other industries, soy production would have to be increased to provide for humans with the current levels of consumption.

We would need an extra 158-211 million tonnes of extra soy (given a 20% oil extraction minus the consumption that we currently give to animals).

Even replacing it with palm oil (the most cost-effective oil-producing plant) would still require a growth of 30-40% of the current palm oil production³⁷.

And as we've seen so far, the more crops we produce, the more animals we kill.

Cows and pigs can turn the soybean meal, cellulose and other leftovers into fat. Which makes them a good conduit for animal death reduction.

This study³⁸ shows how if the US went vegan, the cropland needed to grow the food would increase by 60%. And again, with increased cropland, there is a much higher increase in animal deaths due to pesticide use.

So neither in terms of calories, protein, nutrients nor fat, 100% vegan diets would reduce the number of animal deaths.

Statistical analysis:

For the following analysis we have removed the presence of pasture raised grass fed/finished animals. We also did not count for the possibility of animals being fed crop waste at the farm level or the consumer level. These absences are here to give vegan diets the best possible chance. We have compared Vegan diets vs Omnivore diets that include animals eating an 84% non-human edible feed diet.

We performed a Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis (N = 20,000 iterations) to quantify how uncertainty in input parameters affected estimated animal deaths per 1 million kcal for vegan and omnivorous diets. Each uncertain parameter (e.g., pesticide-related mortality multiplier, slaughter deaths per Mcal, animal-calorie share) was represented by a probability distribution based on literature ranges. Random draws were sampled from these distributions and the resulting deaths per Mcal were computed for each iteration. The simulation produced distributions of possible outcomes and identified which parameters most strongly influenced the difference between vegan and omnivore mortality.

Key model structure

- Vegan deaths per Mcal = crop-harvest deaths per Mcal × pesticide multiplier.
- Omnivore deaths per Mcal = (animal-calorie-share × slaughter deaths per Mcal) + (plant-calorie-share × effective plant deaths per Mcal after upcycling savings).
- Parameters (sampled ranges) were chosen from numbers and qualitative ranges discussed in our paper:
 - slaughter deaths per Mcal (ruminant): 1.0–1.5 (baseline ≈1.255)
 - crop-harvest deaths per Mcal: 1.5–5.0 (AV mid ≈2.1; allowed up to 5)
 - pesticide multiplier: lognormal (median ≈3, long tail) to capture large uncertainty that pesticides multiply harvest deaths
 - animal calorie share (omnivore): 15–40% (previous text cites ~30%)
 - upcycling saving fraction (how much plant-death burden animals avoid): 0–60%

The main quantitative result from this simulation shows the median **vegan deaths to be higher than omnivores** even when being conservative and given the best chance of the vegan diet to succeed. Across 20 000 simulations, the mean vegan mortality rate was 9.3 ± 4.1 deaths/Mcal (95 % CI), vs 6.4 ± 3.7 for omnivorous diets

The probability that a vegan diet will cause more deaths is 97%.

Which assumptions drive the result?

In short: if pesticides substantially multiply crop harvest deaths, the vegan side becomes worse. If the omnivore consumes animals (chickens and pigs) that are fed only on crops, the omnivore side becomes worse. Upcycling (the fraction of plant burden avoided by animals) helps the omnivore case.

To test the robustness of the Monte Carlo results to assumptions about mortality from pesticide use, a sensitivity analysis was conducted in which fixed pesticide multipliers of 1×, 3×, 10×, 30×, and 100× were applied to baseline crop-harvest deaths.

Each multiplier simply represents another proportional increase in the number of animals, assumed to die per unit of crop produced because of pesticide use. For each multiplier, 10,000 simulations were conducted, using the same parameter distributions as in the main model. Results indicate that total mortality increases for both vegan and omnivorous diets as pesticide deaths increase, but the vegan case is more sensitive because it depends completely on crops.

At 1×, both diets produce nearly equal mortality, but from 3× and above, the vegan case exceeds the omnivore in nearly every draw. The probability that vegan deaths exceed omnivore deaths is about ~65% at 1×, >95% at 3×, and approaches 100% at 10× and above.

Thus, we can conclude that the finding that vegan diets may result in more total mortalities for animals under typical agricultural conditions is robust for a range of reasonable assumptions about pesticide effects on all fauna in the field that are explained to be anything that statistically significantly biologically affected by pesticide. This conclusion was reached after giving the best possible chance for vegan foods in commercial sector equating the minimum number of pesticides used (organic) and not including the best possible data for animal foods (organic grass-finished beef).

Rebuttals

The following section presents counter arguments to the points shown above.

Pesticide-free farming + Vertical farming

In order to reduce the use of pesticides, a vertical farm would have to be a building completely isolated so as to avoid any pests (rodents, ants, fruit flies etc.) from attacking the crops.

In the year 2000, there were 2.3 billion acres of harvest land³⁹ (this excludes feed and pasture for animals).

A building of this size is simply not possible given the world's current raw materials production (steel, concrete, copper, plastic etc).

The energy cost of maintaining such a building (lights, automation, humidity control, temperature control, etc.) would also be orders of magnitude greater than current farms that use the sun and nature cycles, with some human input, to grow crops.

A complete replacement of current farms with vertical veganic farming is simply unfeasible with the current technology.

Products derived from such farms would still include non-edible-biomass which could be fed to animals.

As long as current crop farming exists, with pesticide use and plant's grown with non-human edible biomass, the arguments presented in this paper stand as valid.

Veganic farming (outdoor, no animal fertilizer input)

In order to feed the world, current farming practices rely heavily on pesticides, crop protection shootings and fertilisers.

Without animal foods we have seen a need to increase cropland, which would lead to more pesticides being used which would lead to more animal deaths.

Without the animal industry we also would abdicate of natural fertilisers. Meaning that environmental destruction would ramp up⁴⁰. How many animal deaths this would be responsible for does not seem to have been measured.

There is also the issue of limited supply of synthetic fertilizers, and its consequences for the industry if we deplete it.

Without animal or chemical fertilisers, the crop yields would be much smaller. Again, leading to an increased area of cropping and, again, more pesticides having to be used, and more animals being killed.

Cows small feed still causes higher mortality

A common counter-argument is mentioning that animal feed contains small portion of human-edible food (about 14%⁶) still causes more deaths than if we were to give that food to humans. We have touched on this argument previously, but let's elaborate.

This line of argumentation makes three mistakes:

The first is to not account for nutrition only looking at calories. Defenders of this argument will often show a comparison between soy nutrition and meat, but soy is not the only crop fed to animals. According to this source⁴¹, beef cattle only gets about 2% of their feed from soy⁴¹ (not whole, already in a meal form with no oil) out of the total soy that goes to animals, not total soy produced. The rest is mostly wheat, corn and other feedstuff. This would satisfy human caloric needs but not nutritional ones (as seen previously with protein and fat).

Second is to assume that cows are on equal footing for the demand of human-edible crops as chickens and pigs. Beef and dairy together take about 12% of the total soy that goes to animals (not global soy production⁴¹).

However the biggest mistake is that even if we did feed those 14% of crops to humans, there will still be 86% inedible crops leftover which would be available to grow animals with.

An argument could be made that, in the future, emerging tech could make the 86% crop waste human-edible, but no actual data or solutions that can be implemented large scale have been found.

The Grass we Grow

Another popular argument is to say that we grow grass for cows, in which we also use pesticides, since cows can't go to pastures during winter. This point is irrelevant since we have seen the main driver of pesticides is for crops and that, relative to pesticide use⁴², animal foods produce more food with fewer deaths.

But let's say this was not true: it still would not be a good argument. Many places around the world grow cattle without a presence of a freezing/cold winter (such as Argentina, Brazil, Uruguay, parts of Africa, Portugal, Spain, etc.)

We would argue that even with the presence of winter, where grass would be unavailable for part of the year, an animal farmer could put the cows in pastures during spring/summer/autumn and during the Winter, feed the cows the leftover crops and inedible materials that humans produce.

Cow harvest loss

Some may argue, as presented by this source³⁵, that the 1.255 cow deaths per 1Mcals is an optimistic number since there is some loss between the live cow and the usable carcass.

The numbers given by PennState Extension are for the retail cuts only, as stated by the source: *"Yield grading provides an estimate of the percentage of boneless, closely trimmed retail cuts from the four beef primal cuts (chuck, rib, loin, and round)."*

Since such sources only account for retail cuts and do not account for other sources of nutrients or calories, and well as uses of leather and by-products, such an argument lacks power to shift the narrative.

The "Animal Visuals" source ignored the vast amount of waste from crop productions (anywhere between 10-60%)³⁶ and so more data needs to be collected before a comparison regarding waste will be assessed. This paper, however, gave Vegan diets the best possible chance to reach its conclusions.

Biodiversity Loss:

Pastoral systems can cause soil compacting, altering of vegetation and extensive grazing can even lead to habitat destruction⁴³. However, the "Holistic planned Grazing System" coined by Allan Savory has seen great success in restoring rather than destroying.

The same argument could be made about intensive crop farming destroying the environment through topsoil loss. The key is to manage both these systems without over-usage.

Historically Eurasian steppe pastoralists spent 5000+ years of horse-cattle-sheep herding, proving that it can be done sustainably. They were not unique as other historical populations did the same such as East African pastoralists (e.g., Maasai, Samburu) for at least 3,000 years as well as Arabian and North African pastoralists (Bedouin, Berber) for at least 4,000 years.

Biotechnological Fermentation and Lab-Meat

The following paper⁴⁴ states:

"Co-production of single cell protein (SCP) and lipid from lignocellulose-derived carbohydrates and inorganic ammonia offers a promising alternative for poultry or aquaculture feeds. An engineered oleaginous yeast Trichosporon cutaneum MP11 showed great potential for producing SCP and lipid from wheat straw and ammonia sulfate with minimum nutrient input".

This is one of many examples that show biotech fermentation great future promise and will, no doubt, be part of our diets in a not-so-distant future. Whether this can be scaled for worldwide use is uncertain. Although less risky of a process than cultured cells, this type of fermentation still relies on large bioreactors, control of temperature, PH, aeration, agitation and handling of waste of gases and residues.

Lab-meat is an exciting new technology that. Just like Biotech fermentation, may help veganism fight the non-edible plant waste and tip the scales in the vegan way. This technology is currently being developed and is yet to be proven to be viable in large scale. The resulting food products coming from such technologies lack the nutritional value of traditional grown animal foods which is a factor to consider.

There are still many uncertainties regarding this technology, and it cannot be used in the decision-making process as we find it today since, the regular consumer, would not have access to such products.

Limitations:

This VAMAR analysis has several limitations that should be recognised when interpreting results.

This paper treats all animals' deaths as the same with no moral difference between insects, mammals and birds. Someone who is looking for an ethical answer to the question of animal deaths may ignore insect deaths due to the limited research on their consciousness. We tried showing that, the increase in cropland, would also result in birds and mammals dying due to pesticides and crop protection, but data is limited in this regard. We recognize it as a limitation; however, the purpose of this paper was to show if veganism would reduce the number of deaths, and it seems it does not.

Another limitation of this paper is the inaccurate measurements of inedible vs edible biomass that is fed to animals. The studies used in this paper to support the 86%-14% ratio, for example, are based on approximations that will vary depending on region or season. We do not have a factual number of how much for the food that we feed to animals could be fed to humans.

Pesticide use was evaluated primarily based on quantity used per food obtained. This approach ignores different types of pesticides that can be used and how they affect the animal death differently. We correlated pesticide use with animal deaths, but we do not supply a defensible mortality coefficient (number of animals killed per kg of active ingredient). Without this conversion, the "crop pesticides kill more animals" argument remains intuitive, not quantified. Research in this matter is limited. The small amount of research that does exist seems to support this intuitive reasoning.

Pesticide "drift"⁴⁵ and run-off was not evaluated in our study. The destructive impact of this run-off is recognized^{46 47} and would, most likely, have an impact on this paper, adding an extra layer to the cropland increase. However, no actual data relating pesticide run-off and animal deaths was found.

While ruminant systems have advantages in upcycling and pesticide reliance, they carry uncertainties as well: methane emissions, grazing pressure, and variation in pasture management quality. These factors are beyond the scope of this paper but deserve acknowledgement.

Finally, all calculations assume current agronomic technology and global food demand patterns. Future developments in crop diversification or alternative protein sources could alter the relative mortality profiles of plant- and animal-based food systems. Therefore, the results presented here should be viewed as conditional on the present structure of agriculture rather than as definitive predictions of all possible future systems and technologies.

Conclusion

This analysis challenges the idea that vegan diets minimise harm to animals. When accounting for the full range of total mortality across agricultural systems (direct deaths from harvest, deaths from pesticides, habitat displacement, non-human-edible biomass conversion, and harvest system). Then, plant-based systems inflict more total animal deaths than mixed systems or systems that include ruminants.

The role ruminants, particularly pasture-raised cattle, play as biological “upcyclers” is valuable. They convert pasture, plant residues and non-human-edible biomass into high-quality, bioavailable nutrients, and do so indirectly through land that is unsuitable for direct crop production. This process lessens the reliance on cropland that is pesticide intensive and reduces direct and indirect mortality.

Other methods such as food waste fed and inedible biomass-fed animal agriculture are variables that would also reduce animal deaths. This last point could be made irrelevant if food waste would stop existing or emerging technologies would manage to convert these items to human-edible food.

For these reasons, if all animal products were replaced with plant-based foods, there would be an increase in the expanse of cropland, synthetic fertiliser, and pesticides used. This would then lead to negative impacts on biodiversity and animal populations. Replacing animal-derived fats and proteins with plant products like soybean or palm oil would require the conversion of millions of additional hectares and additional industrial inputs, which will worsen the environmental burden.

Working with the current technology and agronomic conditions, a worldwide food system that is solely plant-based would increase animal mortality and increase the disruption to global ecosystems. Sustainable practices must be designed with integrated approaches that include rotational grazing, by-product feeding to ruminants, and the use of less feed made from food for humans. Pesticide use is to be reduced in both crops and livestock sectors to promote integrated systems.

For the average consumer in the United States, Canada and Europe, choosing animal foods rather than Vegan foods would reduce their animal death rate with a 60-97% certainty and, if choosing organic pasture, grass-finished beef, this certainty will be close to 100%. The only option for vegan foods that could, possibly, produce a smaller death toll would be foods that were grown using veganic practices (no fertilizer, no pesticides, indoor) which are not available for the average consumer.

Minimising the harm and risk of food production to animals, demands a careful optimisation of the synergy between animals, crops and ecosystems – not the removal of animal agriculture.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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